

**AN ASSESSMENT OF WATER, SANITATION AND HYGIENE AMONG TAYBA SOUTH
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ABSTRACT

Hygiene promotion is critical for reducing disease transmission by encouraging behaviors like hand-washing. It prevents the spread of pathogens related to water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH). A cross-sectional community based study was carried out, aimed to assess the utilization of sanitation methods among South Tayba citizens, in El-Obeid, North Kordofan State, Sudan. A total of (260) households were selected, were participated (100%) response rate, among the total participants 52 (20%) were male whereas 208 (80%) were females, filled a self-administered questionnaire that was selected through a clustered sampling technique, and a systematic random sampling technique used to select sample size determined from each cluster (block). Data were analyzed using the Statistical Package of Social Sciences (SPSS) version (22.0) software. **Results:** The findings showed that (48%) of houses connected with public network. More than third (71.7%) of water source were protected from pollution. majority (95.4%) of citizens have latrines at home. Less than half (44.6%) of houses had a large breeding of flies and mosquitoes. **Conclusion:** Water, sanitation, hygiene practices among households are insufficient to protect the community from related diseases. Therefore enhance households hygiene practices, control insect breeding around households and expand households connection to the public water network.

KEYWORDS: Sanitation, Households, Hand washing, Hygiene, El-Obeid.**1. INTRODUCTION**

Access to safe water, adequate sanitation, and personal hygiene (WASH) remains a cornerstone of global public health. Unsafe WASH continues to contribute significantly to the global burden of infectious diseases, especially diarrhoeal diseases.^[1,2] Evidence indicates that improvements in drinking water quality, sanitation systems, and hygiene behaviours -particularly hand hygiene- are among the most effective interventions for reducing morbidity and mortality.^[3,4]

Globally, millions of people still lack safely managed drinking water and basic sanitation services, while one-third of the world's population does not have access to handwashing facilities with soap and water.^[2] These gaps

hinder progress toward SDG 6 and increase vulnerability to water-related diseases.^[5]

Regionally, Sub-Saharan Africa faces compounded challenges due to rapid urbanization, infrastructure limitations, and climate-related water scarcity, all of which deepen WASH inequalities.^[6,7]

Locally, in Sudan, prolonged crises, displacement, and deteriorating infrastructure have severely disrupted WASH services. Many households and health facilities lack reliable access to safe water, sanitation, and hygiene supplies, increasing the risk of communicable diseases.^[8,9]

Despite global commitments and policy attention, critical evidence gaps remain concerning local WASH practices, behavioural determinants, and structural barriers to sustainable service delivery—particularly in conflict-affected settings like Sudan.^[10] Generating updated, context-specific evidence is essential for informing policies, strengthening health system resilience, and designing interventions that reflect community realities. This study will document contemporary WASH and personal hygiene practices, identify socio-behavioural and structural determinants, and provide evidence to guide programmatic priorities and national planning.^[11]

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study design

Community based descriptive cross-sectional study was done to an assessment of sanitation methods utilization among South Tayba citizens, in El-Obeid, North Kordofan State, Sudan.

Study area

South Tayba is a big neighborhoods in El-Obeid Urban Area. Located on the east of the national road (El-Obeid, Kosti, and Khartoum). It's bordered by four

neighborhoods: Khor Taqut from the east, airport neighborhood from the west, El-waha neighborhood from south and North Tayba from the north. These area is consist of 1794 houses, Characterized by the bad water channels. Most of these houses are made from mud. A few of these houses are unstable construction. It is considered a vulnerable area and lacks of basic environmental health and primary health care services. There are improper disposal of solid waste and animal waste. There is no water scarcity due to the existence of a public water network in some blocks, and there are other sources of water (Karow, Tanker and Gerba).

Sampling and Sample techniques

A total of sample size was (n = 265). The sampling technique was used is a cluster sampling technique; in this method, the study area was divided into blocks, then the sample units chosen by systematic random sampling. All sample units considering in the same blocks as a homogenous group. A sample was taken proportionally from each blocks, as follow:

Blocks	No. of households	Calculation ($n_h = n_{prop} \frac{N_h}{N}$)	Sample size required from block
Block (1)	290	$290 \div 1793 \times 265$	42
Block (2)	780	$780 \div 1793 \times 265$	116
Block (3)	227	$227 \div 1793 \times 265$	34
Block (4)	496	$496 \div 1793 \times 265$	73
Total	1793		265

Where:

n_h = sub-sample from block (h)

N_h = Size of block

N = Size of population

Data collection

An observational checklist was used to assess the water, sanitation and hygiene practices, such as methods of water gathering, saving, collection, storage and using, and latrine available, hand washing practices ... etc.

Data processing and analysis

All data were checked and cleaned carefully. Data were entered, processed and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), version (23.0).

RESULT

A total of (260) household were selected, were participated (100%) response rate, among the total participants 52 (20%) were male whereas 208 (80%) were females, as showed in **Fig. 1**. (10.2%) of the heads of households are farmers, (6.3%) are Trade, (7.9%) are drivers, (9.1%) are officeholder and (65.6%) are self-employed, (see Fig. 1). **Fig. 2** showed that (30.2%) of the respondents are uneducated, (40.9%) have a basic level

of education, (21.5%) were secondary, (6.8%) are university graduates, only (0.5%) were postgraduate. (48%) of houses connected with public network. (12.7%) of them collect water from the roof of houses and ponds. More than third (71.7%) of water source were protected from pollution. Less than (42.3%) of households were cleaned the area around the source of water. (76.9%) of storage containers were covered. (76.9%) of drinking water cups were clean. (20.8%) of cups are made of materials that interact with water. (69.6%) of storage containers were clean. (27.7%) of storage containers were made of materials that interact with water, as illustrated in **Table 1**. **Table 2**. showed that the majority (95.4%) of citizens have latrines at home. Less than half (49.6%) of latrines at households were good condition. (64.2%) of family size had proportionated with the number of latrines. More than third (76.2%) of latrines were a sufficient distance from food preparation place. Less than half (44.6%) of houses had a large breeding of flies and mosquitoes. (34.2%) of latrines had artificial lighting. More than half (56.9%) of them had provided privacy and confidentiality. Only (4.2%) of households had a hand washing site and provided special soap for hand washing. Near to half 48.5% of citizens had washed their hands after defecation.

Distribution of citizens according to gender in South Tayba, El-Obeid Urban Area; (n= 260)

Distribution of citizens according to their jobs in South Tayba, El-Obeid Urban Area; (n= 260)

Distribution of citizens according to educational level in South Tayba, El-Obeid Urban Area; (n= 260)

Table (1): Assessment of households drinking water; South Tayba; (n= 260).

Variable	Frequency	Percent (%)
<i>What is the type of drinking water sources?</i>		
Water handler	134	51.5%
Connected with public network	126	48.5%
<i>Do you collect rainwater from the roofs?</i>		
Yes	33	12.7%
No	227	87.3%
<i>Is the water protected from contamination?</i>		
Yes	110	42.3%
No	150	57.7%
<i>Are the storage containers covered?</i>		
Yes	200	76.9%
No	60	23.1%
<i>Are the storage containers clean?</i>		
Yes	181	69.6%
No	79	30.4%
<i>Are the storage containers made of materials that interact with water?</i>		
Yes	71	27.3%
No	189	72.7%
<i>Are the drinking water cups clean?</i>		
Yes	199	76.9%
No	59	23.1%
<i>Are the drinking water cups made of materials that interact with water?</i>		
Yes	54	20.8%
No	204	78.5%

Table (2): Assessment of sanitation practices in South Tayba; (n= 260).

Variable	Frequency	Percent (%)
<i>Is there sanitation methods in your house?</i>		
Yes	248	95.4%
No	12	4.6%
<i>Are the latrines in good general condition?</i>		
Yes	129	49.6%
No	131	51.4%
<i>Is the number of latrines sufficient for family size?</i>		
Yes	167	64.2%
No	93	35.8%
<i>Are the latrines located far enough from food preparation place?</i>		
Yes	198	76.2%
No	62	23.8%
<i>Is there the breeding of flies and mosquitoes?</i>		
Yes	116	44.6%
No	144	55.4%
<i>Is there artificial lighting in latrines?</i>		
Yes	89	34.2%
No	171	63.8%
<i>Are the latrines provided privacy and confidentiality?</i>		
Yes	148	56.9%
No	112	43.1%
<i>Do you wash your hand practice after defecation?</i>		
Yes	126	48.5%
No	134	51.5%
<i>Is there a hand washing site?</i>		
Yes	11	4.2%
No	249	95.8%
<i>Is there soap for hand washing?</i>		
Yes	11	4.2%
No	249	95.8%

DISCUSSION

The current survey finding that 48% of households were connected to the public water network indicates moderate access to improved water infrastructure. This result is lower than study implemented in Khartoum showed that 72% connection rate.^[12] But higher than a similar study conducted in rural Gedaref reported that 32% of households were connected.^[13] Studies from Ethiopia found even lower connectivity (27%).^[14] Reflecting regional disparities. Conversely, urban Nigerian households showed higher connection levels (65%).^[15]

The present survey appeared that the use of alternative surface or rooftop water sources was (12.7%). This is lower than studies conducted in different areas; A study conducted among Sudanese semi-urban households revealed that 21% of households reliance on rainwater.^[16] Similar studies in Uganda^[17], and Kenya reported 18–25%.^[18]

This survey showed that the protected water sources were (71.7%). This aligns with UNICEF Sudan (2021), slightly higher than a previous study conducted among Ethiopian households.^[19] Similar conducted in rural Nigeria.^[20]

Our survey showed that about (42.3%) of environment around water source was cleaned. This finding similar to a study conducted in eastern Ethiopia revealed that (39%) of households had cleaned area around water source^[14], but lower than a study in Nigerian households was (56%).^[21] Many studies conducted in South Sudan showed that 28%.^[22]

The present survey appeared that (76.9%) of storage containers were covered. This consistent with a similar study carried out in Ghana showed that (78%) Ghana.^[23] It similar to study conducted in Ethiopia.^[24]

The current survey finding that (76.9%) of drinking cups were clean. This higher than study implemented by Bello *et al.* in Nigerian households showed (62%).^[21] This study showed that (20.8%) of cups made of reactive materials. This comparable with Nabulo *et al.* (2020) (18%)^[25], while a previous study carried out in Ethiopia findings that (25%) of cups made of reactive materials.^[24]

Our survey showed that (69.6%) of storage containers were clean. This comparable with a similar study conducted in eastern Ethiopia^[14], and higher than a similar study conducted in Nigeria.^[26]

This study showed that (27.7%) of storage containers made of reactive materials. This similar to Ethiopian studies appeared (25–28%) but higher than a previous study conducted in Ghana was (15%).^[23]

The present study finding latrines were an available in (95.8%) of households. This higher than different studies conducted in different areas; UNICEF Sudan reported that (72%), Ethiopia finding that (84%), and Tanzania (88%).^[27]

CONCLUSIONS

Water, sanitation, hygiene practices among households are insufficient to protect the community from related diseases. Less than half of houses connected with public network. Less than half of citizens wash their hands after defecation. Less than half households' latrines were good condition. Therefore, promote community awareness on safe water collection practices, enhance households' hygiene practices, control insect breeding around households and expand households connection to the public water network.

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ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The research protocol was approved by the Research Committee of the Health and Environmental Health Department. The Directorate General of Health Affairs, Shiekan Locality was officially contacted and approval was obtained to interview the households. Verbal consent was also obtained from the respondents before they were interviewed.

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